

Exploring Fungal-Induced Mineralization for Crack Healing in Cementitious Composites

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Abstract:

Fungal-induced mineralization is a promising pathway for healing cracks in cementitious materials, yet quantitative, time-resolved monitoring of healing remains limited. This study evaluates two filamentous fungi (*Neurospora crassa* and *Aspergillus niger*) selected based on the mineral precipitation screening in urea-calcium media, where XRD indicates distinct mineral products (calcite for *N. crassa* and calcium oxalate for *A. niger*). Mortar cylinders (50.8 mm × 101.6 mm) were pre-cracked using controlled splitting tensile loading to generate cracks. Healing was conducted for up to 112 days, and additional specimens were maintained as controls at the same age to isolate the healing effect by bacteria and fungi. Healing progression was tracked using shear-wave velocity measurements (bender elements) at multiple time points through one quadrimester (112 days). At 112 days, compressive strength tests were performed on both healed and non-healed specimens to assess mechanical property recovery attributable to healing. Preliminary results indicate that, at 112 days, the healed specimens exhibited higher compressive strength than age-matched non-healed controls, with fungal-treated groups averaging approximately 70% higher strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Cracking is a common and unavoidable issue in cementitious materials and, while it may not immediately reduce load capacity, it can substantially compromise durability by providing pathways for water and gases (e.g., CO₂) to ingress and attack embedded steel reinforcement (Jin et al., 2018). Microbially Induced Carbonate Precipitation (MICP) has therefore attracted attention as a promising self-healing strategy, and fungal-based approaches are particularly promising because fungi can promote calcium mineral precipitation; for example, fungi have been reported to induce CaCO₃ precipitation even under concrete-relevant alkalinity, and urease-positive *Neurospora crassa* can deposit CaCO₃ on mortar surface via MICP with a dense biomineralized mycelial network (Menon et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2022). Within this TRANS-IPIC project, we further explored fungal-induced mineralization (FIM) as a pathway to heal cracks and improve durability of the cementitious materials.

1.2 Knowledge gaps

Many self-healing studies emphasize endpoint results after healing, whereas quantitative, time-resolved monitoring of healing progression remains limited. What is less common is tracking how healing evolves over time with a quantitative signal. Wave-based monitoring is useful here because wave speed changes when cracks open or when cracks get filled, so it can capture internal healing without breaking specimens (Tsangouri et al., 2015). In this study, we use bender elements to measure the shear-wave velocity (V_s) of the cement mortars to monitor healing about four months (112 days), and then we verify the healing process at 112 days by comparing compressive strength of the healed specimens to the non-healed controls. To our knowledge, this study is among the earliest efforts to incorporate filamentous fungi into the cementitious mortar and to quantify crack healing progression.

1.3 Objectives

This study evaluates fungal-induced mineralization for crack healing using two filamentous fungi (*Neurospora crassa* and *Aspergillus niger*) selected from the precipitation screening. The objectives are to (i) track healing progression using time-resolved shear-wave velocity measurements through 112 days, and (ii) quantify mechanical recovery by comparing 112-day compressive strength of the healed specimens against age-matched non-healed controls. In addition, after an initial healing period of four weeks, specimens were intentionally dried for approximately four weeks to examine how interruption and subsequent resumption of the healing environment influence crack-healing performance.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Fungal and bacterial strains

Filamentous fungi have attracted growing interest as bio-based self-healing agents for cementitious materials because their interconnected hyphal networks can provide abundant nucleation sites for mineral precipitation within cracks (Van Wylick et al., 2021). However, prior screening work indicates that fungal viability and mineralization are highly strain-dependent under concrete-relevant conditions, motivating a precipitation-based selection prior to mortar healing tests (Menon et al., 2019).

In this study, three filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus niger* ATCC 9029, *Neurospora crassa* FGSC 2489, and *Trichoderma reesei* ATCC 13631) were screened in a urea–calcium cementation solution, and precipitates were identified by X-ray Diffraction (XRD). The screening indicated distinct mineral products—calcite (CaCO₃) for *N. crassa* and calcium oxalate (CaC₂O₄) for *A. niger*—whereas *T. reesei* showed no detectable calcium-based mineral precipitation; therefore, *N. crassa* and *A. niger* were selected for subsequent crack-

healing experiments. To benchmark fungal healing against a well-tested microbial healing strategy, *Sporosarcina pasteurii* (SP) was also included as a ureolytic, bacteria-mediated healing reference system in the experimental matrix.

2.2 Specimens and mix design

Mortar was prepared at a cement:sand:liquid mass ratio of 1:1.5:0.4. The mixing liquid consisted of a mineralization reactant solution and a microbial medium. Group-wise compositions and per-specimen dosing volumes are summarized in Table 1.

Mortar samples were used to avoid potential interference from coarse aggregates in subsequent characterization and to improve experimental controllability (Zhao et al., 2022). Mortar cylinders with a diameter of 50.8 mm and a height of 101.6 mm were prepared using ordinary Portland cement, sand, and water at a mass ratio of 1:1.5:0.4 (cement:sand:water). Mixing was performed using a mechanical mortar mixer following a staged protocol: dry blending of cement and sand at low speed (60 s), manual scraping of the mixing pot, additional low-speed mixing (30 s), gradual addition of water over 30 s at medium speed, followed by 30 s at medium speed. For fiber- and bio-treated sample groups, cellulose-based fibers, mineralization reactant solution and microbial suspensions were introduced during mixing and blended at high speed for 60 s, followed by final homogenization at high speed for 5–6 min. Fresh mortar was cast into cleaned cylindrical molds, tapped 15–20 times to reduce entrapped air, leveled, covered with plastic sheets, and cured at 22°C and >90% relative humidity for 28 days prior to crack induction and healing tests. The mixing procedure was aligned with ASTM C305-06. Final sample numbers for each test are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Sample mix design

Group	Treatment	Fiber (vol%)	OPC (g)	Sand (g)	Fiber (g)	Total liquid (mL)	Solution 1 (mL)	Solution 2 (mL)	Solution 2 type
Control	Blank control	0	160.4	240.7	0.0	64.2	42.8	21.4	PDB base
SP	<i>S. pasteurii</i>	0	160.4	240.7	0.0	64.2	42.8	21.4	Bacterial base + inoculum
SPF	<i>S. pasteurii</i> + fiber	0.45	160.4	240.7	1.0	64.2	42.8	21.4	Bacterial base + inoculum
ANF	<i>A. niger</i> + fiber	0.45	160.4	240.7	1.0	64.2	42.8	21.4	PDB base + fungal inoculum
NCF	<i>N. crassa</i> + fiber	0.45	160.4	240.7	1.0	64.2	42.8	21.4	PDB base + fungal inoculum

Solution 1 was the mineralization reactant solution containing urea and calcium nitrate tetrahydrate $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 380.84 g/L each. The solution was prepared by mixing equal volumes of urea stock and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ stock solutions made at the same mass concentration. For Control/ANF/NCF, Solution 2 used 24 g/L PDB as the base medium, with fungal inoculum added for ANF and NCF and no inoculum for Control. For SP/SPF, Solution 2 used a bacterial base medium consisting of 0.13 M Tris buffer at pH 9.0 with 20 g/L yeast extract and 10 g/L ammonium sulfate, with *Sporosarcina pasteurii* inoculum, following Lin et al. (2016). Bacterial and fungal inocula were prepared following the standard workflow of culturing, centrifugation-based concentration, and resuspension in fresh base medium prior to mixing.

Table 2. Experimental matrix and sample numbers

Group	Treatment Group	Sample Numbers		
		28 days	Healed samples	Unhealed samples
Control	Blank (no microorganism)	4	6	3
SP	<i>Sporosarcina pasteurii</i>	3	5	3
SPF	<i>S. pasteurii</i> + cellulose-based fiber	9	5	3
ANF	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> + cellulose-based fiber	3	3	3
NCF	<i>Neurospora crassa</i> + cellulose-based fiber	3	4	3

2.3 Crack generation

Cracks were introduced using controlled splitting tensile test loading to generate a single dominant crack while avoiding complete specimen separation. Specimens were loaded diametrically in a universal testing machine, and the test was continuously monitored and automatically terminated using a break-detection threshold set to 60% (i.e., loading was stopped once the post-peak load dropped to 60% of the maximum load). This setting was selected to limit unintended damage and to stop loading shortly after crack initiation. Crack widths were verified using image-based measurements with a reference scale (Medeiros and Di Sarno, 2024).

2.4 Healing protocol and control design

After crack generation, specimens in each group were divided into two subsets: (i) a healing subset subjected to a wet–dry cycling regimen for up to 112 days, and (ii) an age-matched non-healed control subset. For the healing subset, specimens were immersed in tap water during the wet phase and then exposed to air during the dry phase; one cycle lasted 2 days (wet + dry). Age-matched non-healed controls were cracked using the same procedure and stored for the same duration under the same temperature range without undergoing the wet–dry cycling treatment, to isolate the healing contribution by bacteria and fungi from ongoing hydration/aging effects in cement. Specimens were stored and handled by group in separate containers to minimize cross-contamination.

2.5 Shear-wave testing

Bender-element shear-wave testing was used to track internal crack healing by measuring shear-wave velocity (V_s). To standardize measurement locations relative to the crack plane, measurements were conducted on the specimen side surface along two vertical lines oriented normal to the crack interface. The specimen height was divided into three equal segments, and the midpoint of each segment was used as the measurement location. A square-wave excitation (20 Hz, 5 V) was applied, and responses were acquired using a digital oscilloscope with 128-signal stacking. Signals were band-pass filtered (100 Hz–50 kHz), and the first-arrival time was identified from the waveform. V_s was computed as the sensor spacing divided by the travel time. Measurements were performed at multiple time steps for 112 days. The results were not reported in this paper due to the page limitation.

2.6 Compression testing

Compressive strength was measured on the cylindrical specimens following ASTM C39 and calculated as peak load divided by the cross-sectional area. Baseline compressive strength at 28 days was obtained prior to crack induction. At 112 days, compressive tests were conducted on healed specimens and non-healed controls to quantify healing-related recovery. Final sample numbers are shown in Table 2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Strength recovery

Figure 1 compares 112-day compressive strength of healed specimens against age-matched non-healed controls. The blank control increased from 19.0 MPa to 28.6 MPa, corresponding to a 9.6 MPa increase (50.5%). The fungal-treated groups showed larger absolute recovery, with ANF increasing from 53.9 MPa to 94.9 MPa, a 41.0 MPa increase (76.1%), and NCF increasing from 43.6 MPa to 71.2 MPa, a 27.6 MPa increase (63.3%). The bacterial benchmark groups exhibited smaller absolute gains overall, with SP increasing from 13.8 MPa to 17.0 MPa, a 3.2 MPa increase (23.2%), and SPF from 10.1 MPa to 18.2 MPa, an 8.1 MPa increase (80.2%). Overall, the treated-versus-age-matched comparison indicates a treatment-dependent recovery response, with the strongest strength restoration observed for ANF.

Figure 1. Compressive strength comparison between unhealed and healed samples.

4. CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Key conclusions

Overall, the results support fungal-induced mineralization as a promising pathway for autonomous crack healing in cementitious mortar under wet–dry exposure.

- (1) Two fungal strains were selected through precipitation screening, and project XRD evidence indicates calcite formation by *Neurospora crassa* and calcium oxalate formation by *Aspergillus niger*.
- (2) Compressive strength measured after 112-day wet–dry cycles increased for all groups, including the blank control, indicating that hydration and moisture conditioning contribute to partial recovery.
- (3) The fungal-treated groups exhibited 13%–26% larger strength recovery than the blank control, with the strongest response in ANF and a clear improvement in NCF.

4.2 Future work

Future work will perform XRD and TGA analysis to distinguish mineral precipitation products from hydration-related phase evolution during wet–dry cycling. In addition, the crack surfaces have been systematically photographed during the experiments, and subsequent work will quantify crack healing using image-based metrics such as crack width and crack closure ratio. These microstructural and visual assessments will be coupled with the time-resolved Vs response and compressive recovery to build a more complete linkage between bio-mineralization, cement hydration, crack filling, and strength restoration.

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